

Search for Rigor in User Research

An Analysis of User Research Literature in Design

Isil Oygur

*Doctor of Design Candidate, Interdisciplinary Design Institute, Washington State University
Spokane, WA, USA, isil_oygur@wsu.edu*

Abstract: Designing pleasant user experiences requires a wide spectrum of knowledge and input from a broad range of theories and research methods from various disciplines. In the field of user research, social sciences have informed and reshaped the once intuitive design process into a systematic activity by bringing more rigor into design research. In this process, various new methods have entered into design territory. These methods sometimes lose their connection to their origins; at other times, they gain additional meaning in their new context. In order to better frame user research in design, this paper provides an analysis of research methods from the perspective of the systematic conduct of research. A new classification scheme is introduced as a first step for the refinement of methods and concepts in user research. The proposed scheme extends from intuitive research to systematic research. The mapping on this scheme is project specific. While this approach to analyzing user research landscape provides an alternative taxonomy, this taxonomy is not exhaustive. Nonetheless, it aims to develop an overarching framework for design disciplines to better focus user studies.

Key words: *User research, research methods, user experience, classification scheme.*

1. Introduction

Starting with the early 1960's, one of the central discussions in design was an effort to locate the role of various methodologies in design disciplines. The aim was to "scientise" design [1], and to ground design on empirical, positivist, analytical, and formal basis with the introduction of "a collection of scientific methods and techniques into design" [2]. This movement was later titled "Design Methods Movement" and its advocates were criticized for isolating design from everyday practice that eventually brought no success to the professional act of designing [1]. Nonetheless, the critical perspective provided by the design methods movement had great impact on the development of contemporary design disciplines.

Today, similar to the developments in the 1960's, we are experiencing a search for a more rigorous and systematic process in another area of design research: user research. Research on users was historically a duty of designers [3]. The developments in the field of computer-supported cooperative work [4], the continuing struggle of users with interface designs [5], the insufficient perspective provided by market research [6], and the cost of problematic design decisions for companies [7] have introduced design disciplines to more systematic approaches to user research. Researchers, mostly with a background in the social sciences, have taken the lead in

user research [8]. With the interdisciplinary studies of these researchers, design disciplines have become familiar with methods from other disciplines such as anthropology and sociology. These alien methods sometimes lose their connection to their origins; at other times, they gain additional meaning in their new context. Desmet and Hekkert [9] further explain this phenomenon as follows:

Design research takes a special place because design is an integrated discipline that requires aesthetic, marketing, ergonomic, and engineering skills. This multidisciplinary nature has stimulated the emergence of a variety of terminologies in the realm of design research. In addition to adopting concepts from other disciplines, the design research community has also introduced some new concepts of its own. The result is a research agenda dominated by a multitude of experiential concepts that, to some extent, differ in terms of described affective phenomena, theoretical backgrounds, research purposes, and design possibilities.

The analysis in this paper is based on Desmet and Hekkert's argument. The aim is to analyze the literature on user research within design disciplines on the basis of "intuitive", "semi-systematic" and "systematic" approaches to research. Intuitive methods involve neither qualitative nor quantitative research methods. Instead, intuitive research is designer-centric. Designers develop solutions based on experiential knowledge and their creativity. Semi-systematic research involves a limited amount of qualitative and/or quantitative research that is conducted without empirical and rigorous worries. On the other hand, systematic research requires rigorous conduct of qualitative and/or quantitative research methods. Research procedures and research results should be documented and disseminated so that the research design can be replicated in other contexts with different participants. While making these distinctions, I do not propose "intuitive research" and "systematic research" as binary opposites, but instead view them as two poles of a continuum. The difference is defined by the amount of rigorous approach to research.

In this paper, I will first provide a general perspective and a brief history on user research in design leading to the discussion on intuitive, semi-systematic and systematic approaches. The second section of the paper proposes a classification scheme for user research together with its rational and categorical characteristics. Each category is further explained with examples from design literature. The paper concludes with a summary about the use of the proposed classification scheme.

Before continuing, I also need to clarify the way I will use the term "user research" in this paper. I evaluate user research under the larger umbrella of design research. User research is informed by many domains, and is studied under many disciplines. In this paper, the term is used with a narrower meaning referring to studies that are informed by social sciences and applied by design professionals while developing new products and services.

2.Design Research on Users: The Background

Design research is one of the foundations for 'robust design' which is characterized by agile designers who are equipped with a wide range of knowledge [10]. The sources of this wide range of "knowledge" have been an area of debate in design disciplines. Advocates are divided into two main groups, those who support the superiority of

experiential knowledge and those who support research-based knowledge. The research-based group's approach to design methods has provided us with some of the most in-depth information on the act of designing (two of the influential figures are Christopher Alexander [11] and John Chris Jones [12]). These researchers also aimed at rationalizing design and sharing methods that can guide designers while developing new artifacts. "The reasons advanced for developing new methods often were based on the assumption that modern, industrial design had become too complex for intuitive methods" [1]. As a result, design researchers have concentrated on developing systematic methods that can be replicated while solving design problems.

One of the subfields of design research is also experiencing a similar path of transformation. This subfield is the *research on users* for the development of new products and services. User research is not a new concept for design professions [3,13]. However, since the 1980's, the developments in this field accelerated and new research methods were introduced to design from social sciences.

There are multiple dynamics in play for the increased significance of social science research methods in user research. By the mid twentieth century, companies had started to provide products and services with comparable qualities within a similar price range. The competition in the market forced firms to discover new areas that could give them an advantage based on innovation [6]. Concentrating only on functionality, ergonomics and usability of products and services were not sufficient. Market research had shortcomings as it generated information via quantitative research that did not provide in-depth information on emotional and experiential aspects of artifacts [14,15]. However, it has been realized that intangible attributes, such as emotions and values, are also an essential component of the experiences stemming from artifacts [9,16]. Designers are not always successful in addressing these attributes without research, as socio-economic and cultural changes have further separated designers from the typical users of the products that they design [5]. In short, design problems have become too sophisticated to be solved based solely on designers' assumptions [17].

Design researchers realizing these changes in the field, have tried to find other methods to reach user insights and have concentrated on methods for user involvement. Studies in the real-life contexts of users via research methods, such as ethnography and contextual inquiry, provide valuable information on what people *do* and *say* [14,18]. The data gathered can be even more in-depth with the active participation of users in the process. One such participation occurs through the introduction of two or three dimensional tools to build mockups or to develop moodboards that provide a chance for people to express what they want through the artifacts they *make* [14].

As a chain effect of all the developments, today there is a wide variety of research and literature where design, research, and users intersect. The boundaries are difficult to establish because of the multi-disciplinary character of the subject. In addition to design disciplines, some of the other domains that inform the field include anthropology, marketing, sociology, psychology, behavioral psychology, management information systems, and cognitive sciences.

Each of these disciplines introduces its unique perspective, concepts, and research methods to design disciplines. Since the traditional skill-based design schools do not always educate designers on systematic conduct of user research, individuals, most with a background in social sciences, take the lead in the field [8]. These researchers have introduced designers and design disciplines to a new form of design research that is more systematic. Artifacts, developed based on systematic research, have an increased chance of being successful on the market because these products are grounded on user needs, emotions, experiences, and values. The success stories of products and services developed by firms such as IDEO [19] and Steelcase [18] support the significance of systematic research. As a result, even in the absence of trained design researchers, designers try to fill the gap and become user advocates [20]. Consequently, today we have a wide range of methods applied by designers and design researchers to incorporate user input into design.

3. A New Classification Scheme for User Research

In its multi-disciplinary environment, user research becomes the pot in which various methods are blended and presented on a new landscape. The nature of the new terrain differentiates depending on researchers' approach to user research. There are only a limited number of studies that endeavor to map this diverse field. To list a few, Hanington [21], Plowman [22], Rohrer [23], and Sanders [8,24] previously worked on classifying user research methods. Each of these scholars concentrated on different aspects of research methods. For example, Sanders mapped methods based on “the impetus of the design research approaches” and “the mindset of those who practice and teach design research” [8], whereas Plowman [22] took a closer look into ethnography and grouped its research tools as being visual or verbal and quantitative or qualitative.

While all existing classifications of user research methods are valuable, these taxonomies generally do not include methods used by both designers and design researchers. For example, Sanders, Rohrer and Plowman provide the perspective of design researchers. They do not include the methods developed and applied exclusively by designers. While Hanington's perspective comes out of human-centered design [21], his model does not differentiate between the various modes of application of these methods.

3.1. From Intuitive Research to Systematic Research

Illustration 1 maps a conceptual framework that unites user research approaches applied both by designers and design researchers. In this framework, user research approaches are mapped on a single axis (a continuum) ranging from intuitive to systematic research; two not being binary opposites. Instead, a more complete picture of the design problem can be framed when there is a combination of intuitive, semi-systematic, and systematic research in the process.

Illustration 1 – The continuum of user research specific to design

The mapping on this continuum is different from the previous classifications in the sense that it is project (case) specific. Each research method can be located on various points of this continuum based on its application. This classification scheme works as an umbrella over existing topologies. For example, Plowman’s typography of ethnography represents a social scientist’s perspective [22] and can be placed into either semi-systematic or systematic category based on the research design of a project.

While the historical search for rigor in design serves as the foundation of this conceptual framework, other variables in this continuum are the number of research methods applied, dominance of designers and design researchers in the process, pleasant user experiences, and unexpected failures (Illustration 2). These variables are closely linked.

Illustration 2 – The rationale of the continuum

From left to right on the continuum, the probability of developing pleasant user experiences increases; whereas the chance of having unexpected market failures decreases as a result of experience-based design solutions. The number of methods applied in a triangulation fashion and the conduct of research with a wider population play significant roles with increased success on the right side of the continuum. In this case, increased success corresponds to better framing of user needs and useful incorporation of research results in design solutions. There is no consensus on the required amount of research in order to frame a problem holistically for successful design outcomes [25]. However, as with any other field, as the research sample increases, the study reaches theoretical saturation and the generalizability of research findings increase [26].

Another consequence associated with increased systematic research is less creativity [27] on the right end of the continuum. The dominance of design researchers over designers in the process and arriving at design decisions based on research findings rather than intuition, are two of the reasons for the loss of creativity and the disenfranchisement of the designer. On the contrary, while intuitive approaches are creativity oriented, they are also criticized for a limited contribution to the advancement of the field:

... , if we can’t understand and articulate the conditions that lead to great results, we can’t find ways of improving those results in the future. Moreover, without understanding the conditions of success, there can be no dialogue, no discourse, no sharing of information within the design

field or with other fields and disciplines. . . . The goal is to provide a way for creating the conditions for spark-making more consistently [28].

3.1.1. Intuitive Research

The left end of the continuum is characterized by *intuitive research*. Intuitive research represents the designers' investigation of users based on intuitive methods and experiential knowledge. While systematic research on users is the state of art in design research, it is not the convention [29]. Designers try to compensate for the absence of design researchers either with conducting their own research on users, or by depending on their own intuition and experiences. Rigor, planning of research procedures, and documenting the design process for replication in the future are not important. The explorations take place in designers' minds or with the exchange of knowledge within design teams. The idea is that a designer's personal experience with a product category also represents the users' experiences. Therefore, designers develop solutions based on their personal knowledge and intuition about the use of the end product. This is the traditional design model which fails to develop successful products from time to time as designers' experiences do not necessarily represent the users' experiences in today's diverse culture [30,31]. As a result, products and services developed solely with intuitive research are more vulnerable to unexpected failures in the market.

Research methods, such as self modeling, storyboards, and scenario building, are usually mapped toward the intuitive research end of the continuum as these methods are conducted by designers in their own context without user involvement. However, it should also be noted that these methods can move towards the systematic end of the continuum with the application of more rigor and systematic procedures.

3.1.2. Semi-Systematic Research

Research conducted either by designers or design researchers can be also in the middle of the two poles. This area of the continuum is labeled as *semi-systematic research* on Illustration 1. User research within this category is based on ad-hoc research methods that are neither fully intuitive nor fully systematic. For example, without in-depth empirical and systematic knowledge on conducting observations, designers go into the field and observe the intended user groups. In this process, designers rely on ad-hoc research methods which "tend to overlook things that anthropologists see as important parts of the research process" [32]. Another approach that can be mapped under semi-systematic category, is the research conducted in the presence of design researchers that does not direct as much rigor as systematic research. This type of research is generally condensed and does not aim to generate generalizable research results.

3.1.3. Systematic Research

The goal of *systematic research* is to minimize unexpected failures and maximize the generation of knowledge for developing successful products from the viewpoint of users. In this category, replicable systematic research is conducted throughout the design process. Systematic research generally involves research design with multiple methods. While time and budget limitations do not allow for triangulation, "most design teams benefit from combining insights from multiple research methods" [23].

Research methods such as ethnography, participatory design, focus group studies, ethno-methodology, contextual inquiry, and action research tend to be located closer to the systematic research end of the continuum. Systematic research requires researchers/designers to be trained on these research methods. This specifically trained population is referred to as design researchers. While some designers consider themselves to also be researchers, traditional design education does not train designers with systematic research methods. “The incorporation of user needs into a design is challenging, as gathering and analyzing such intangible and qualitative data requires considerable skill and expertise. With conventional industrial/product design training, undergraduates often do not have the opportunity to obtain and/or develop such skills” [33]. Therefore, systematic research is mostly associated with design researchers who have been trained in areas such as ethnography, environmental behavior research, and cognitive sciences.

The use of the term systematic, rather than empirical or scientific, is significant at the right end of the continuum. Some research methods are transformed to answer the unique needs of design professions [18,22]. In this transformation, methods might lose their scientific and empirical bounds. This situation resembles the critiques of case studies that associate this research method with soft research “possibly because investigators have not followed systematic procedures” [34]. Similarly, research conducted in design may also be criticized for being soft [32]. However, with the systematic approaches to research, the research process can be made explicit and replicable. As a result, the research findings and the research design can be better defended and empirically tested.

4. A Case-Based Approach to Mapping

The proposed classification scheme provides a framework for the reevaluation of user research methods to better analyze the gaps in the field. This continuum is *case-specific*, thus each method can be mapped under several points based on its application in design projects. For example, contextual observations were conducted in two of the projects exemplified in the following pages: the Kindergarten project and Proactive Health project. In these examples, the application of the method differentiated based on who conducted the research and how the observation was performed. Therefore, it is not accurate to associate a research method with a single category. For this reason, I will try to further explain the classification scheme with project examples from design literature as mapped in Illustration 3.

Illustration 3 – Examples for each research category

Intuitive research: The intuitive research end of the continuum represents the traditional design process where the designer is believed to be the lonely genius. A contemporary example for this category is the Juicy Salif (the citrus-fruit squeezer) designed by Phillip Starck. Starck designed this product on a napkin as a result of an instant inspiration over a dinner [35]. There was no user research in this process. While this product is successful in terms of developing emotional connections and is aesthetically pleasing, it has functionality problems because there is no mechanism separating the seeds from the juice. As acid corrodes gold, the gold plated version has a warning note urging users not to squeeze any acidic fruit. Owners of this product mainly use it as a display object [35]. Other examples of this category can be the designs of early software interfaces that created more frustration than solution for their users in the early 1980's. It was the engineers' duty to design user interfaces without any research input. As a result, engineers built systems based on their own systems knowledge, and assumed that an ordinary user without an engineering background could use these complicated interfaces, which was not the case [5]. These two examples are characterized by designers' experience and intuition as the basis for new product concepts.

Intuitive - Semi-systematic research: In order to introduce senior-year interior design students with human-centered design, Danko et al. [36] requested that students apply narrative inquiry at three points in their design process: programming, conceptualization, and presentation phases. The assigned studio project was to design an interior space for a corporate headquarters office or a retail space. Students read, wrote and shared stories. The stories students wrote were fictional. Students did not conduct research prior to their narration. Instead, they created fictional characters and developed scenarios that these characters might encounter in office/retail spaces. Students were expected to develop design solutions based on the hypothetical situations they created. While Danko et al. found the design narratives to be significant for creating empathy with users of these spaces, the design narration method introduced in studio did not focus on real users. This application of narrative inquiry does not include an empirical approach. Still, it is different from the Juicy Salif project in the sense that it prioritizes user experiences. Therefore, Danko et al.'s project is an example of a design process that involves both intuitive and semi-systematic methods.

Semi-systematic research: Different from the first two examples, St Pierre's [37] approach to design includes a research phase. While designing furniture for a kindergarten, Pierre spent time in the kindergarten observing kids and teachers interacting with her early prototypes. St Pierre's observations in this context enabled her to realize that these objects did not only serve as furniture, but that they also functioned as toys for the kids. Children needed stackable furniture so that they could move them around to create their imaginative structures. While her observations helped her to clarify the design problem, she was aware of the fact that she was not conducting research in the style of a trained researcher. That is why, as a second phase of the project, St Pierre hired a researcher to conduct the research for her. This gave her the chance to compare her research approach with that of the trained researcher. While St Pierre tried to avoid emotions to affect her observations, the trained researcher used emotions as an advantage for "giving a resonance to her observations" [37].

St Pierre's research also shows that exemplars and personal experience play a crucial role in design [38]. Her observations in the field enabled her to gain experience on kids' furniture that has proven to be valuable for

innovative design solutions. It might not always be necessary to watch others perform an action to gain experience. A designer might be a participant observer of himself/herself. “Some stunning product ideas come from an engineer or designer who actually uses the products he or she develops because this individual combines knowledge of unexpressed needs with knowledge of how to fill those needs” [6]. I tend to place this type of research under semi-systematic, because it also involves a longitudinal observation rather than instant inspiration or conduct of systematic research on users.

Semi-systematic - Systematic research: A more systematic approach to design is present in a project called Preventing Drug Interactions [39]. This project involved the development of an interactive software for people over sixty. The aim was to educate this group of the effects of harmful drug interactions so that they would be more careful about self-medication and alcohol use while taking medicine. There was no research prior to the development of the concept. Multiple research methods were utilized in the process of the software development. These methods included: surveys, questionnaires, focus group studies, and clinical trials. These enabled the design team to understand the perceptions of this age group and design the software accordingly. For example, in each focus group study, a prototype of the software was introduced to users and their reactions were tested. These insights enabled continuous improvements to the interface design. This project is placed in between semi-systematic and systematic because the research conducted was limited to the evaluation of the software and the process involved a limited amount of triangulation.

Systematic research: The Proactive Health Project at Intel [40] involves a more intensive research process compared to Preventing Drug Interactions. The Proactive Health Project focused on future elders and their concept of healthcare. The background study and evaluative research phases involved expert interviews, literature review, in-house wake-up interviews, camera surveys, focus groups, contextual interviews, shadow studies, longitudinal interviews, and surveys. This research highlighted that “while these groups did ask for medical diagnostic devices and pill reminders, they also demanded tools for psychological supports, promoting good fitness and nutrition, fending off social isolation, coping with loss of memory-hearing-sight and staying engaged in the world with a sense of purpose” [40]. Conduct of multiple research methods with rigor characterized this research as systematic. This method can be applied in other contexts to compare research results and to replicate the research process.

5. Conclusion

User research conducted to inform the design process is one of the fastest growing areas of design research [29]. Various research methods are utilized to gain knowledge of users’ latent needs, experiences and desires. This information is used for developing new products and service concepts to better answer users’ tangible and intangible needs.

While academics and practitioners are giving increased attention to developing and improving user research methods to better serve the needs of design professions, it is also prominent to develop a holistic framework to analyze the landscape of user research. Taxonomy of user research approaches are bringing further clarity to the field and are solving problems related to misunderstanding user research terminology. The classification of user

research approaches is helpful for analyzing the gaps in the field and is serving as a resource for practitioners to plan their research efforts.

The proposed classification scheme in this paper also has the same goals. All research categories mapped on this scheme have significance in design. However, while moving from intuitive research to systematic research, the new knowledge generated through research increases. Systematic research calls for documenting research procedures and enables the validation of research findings with the replication of the same research design in other contexts or with other participants. For this reason, systematic research has an increased value in terms of the collective advancement of the field. On the other hand, each research approach has unique qualities and they bring valuable input to the design process. Each design process can benefit from a combination of intuitive, semi-systematic and systematic research approaches.

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7. References

- [1] Cross, N. (2001). Designerly ways of knowing: design discipline versus design science. *Design Issues*, 17(3), 49-55.
- [2] Buchanan, R. (1995). Rhetoric, humanism and design. In R. Buchanan, & V. Margolin (Eds.), *Discovering design: Explorations in design studies* (pp. 23-57). Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- [3] Rothstein, P. (1999). The “re-emergence” of ethnography in industrial design today. Paper presented at the *Design Education Conference*. Chicago, IL.
- [4] Grønbaek, K., & Mogensen, P. (1997). Informing general CSCW product development through cooperative design in specific work domains. *Computer Supported Cooperative Work*, 6(4), 275-304.
- [5] Norman, D. A. (2002). *The design of everyday things*. New York: Basic Books.
- [6] Leonard, D., & Rayport, J. F. (1997). Spark innovation through empathic design. *Harvard Business Review*, 75(6), 102-113.
- [7] Cagan, J., & Vogel, C. M. (2002). *Creating breakthrough products: Innovation from product planning to program approval*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall PTR.
- [8] Sanders, E. (2006). Design research in 2006. *Design Research Quarterly*, 1(1), 1-8.
- [9] Desmet, P. M. A., & Hekkert, P. (2007). Framework of product experience. *International Journal of Design*, 1(1), 57-66.
- [10] Archer, B. (1999). Viewpoint: Design, innovation, agility. *Design Studies*, 20(6), 565-571.
- [11] Alexander, C. (1964). *Notes on the synthesis of form*. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard University Press.

- [12] Jones, J. C. (1992). *Design methods (2nd edition)*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- [13] Dreyfuss, H. (1955). *Designing for people*. New York: Simon and Schuster.
- [14] Sanders, E. (2002). From user-centered to participatory design approaches. In J. Frascara (Ed.), *Design and the social sciences: Making connections* (pp. 1-8). London; New York: Taylor & Francis.
- [15] Laurel, B. (2003). Muscular design. In B. Laurel (Ed.), *Design research: Methods and perspectives* (pp. 16-19). Cambridge, Mass: The MIT Press.
- [16] Pine II, B. J., & Gilmore, J. H. (1998). Welcome to the experience economy. *Harvard Business Review*, 76(4), 97-106.
- [17] Margolin, V. (1997). Getting to know the user. *Design Studies*, 18(3), 227-236.
- [18] Wasson, C. (2000). Ethnography in the field of design. *Human Organization*, 59(4), 377-388.
- [19] Kelley, T., & Littman, J. (2001). *The art of innovation: Lessons in creativity from IDEO, America's leading design firm*. New York: Doubleday.
- [20] Krippendorf, K. (2005). *The semantic turn: A foundation for design*. Boca Raton: Taylor & Francis.
- [21] Hanington, B. (2003). Methods in the making: A perspective on the state of human research in design. *Design Issues*, 19(4), 9-18.
- [22] Plowman, T. (2003). Ethnography and critical design practice. In B. Laurel (Ed.), *Design research: Methods and perspectives* (pp. 30-48). Cambridge, Mass: The MIT Press.
- [23] Rohrer, C. (2008). When to use which user experience research methods. Available at <http://www.useit.com/alertbox/user-research-methods.html>. [Accessed 18 March, 2009]
- [24] Sanders, E. (2008). An evolving map of design practice and design research. *Interactions*, XV, 13-17.
- [25] Nielsen, J. (2000). Why you only need to test with 5 users. Available at <http://www.useit.com/alertbox/20000319.html>. [Accessed 26 April, 2009]
- [26] Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Chicago, IL: Aldine Transaction.
- [27] Arnold, J. (2006). The reconciliation of research and creativity in industrial design. Paper presented at the *National Education Symposium of the Industrial Designers Society of America*. Austin, TX.
- [28] Cain, J. (1998). Experience-based design: Toward a science of artful business innovation. *Design Management Journal*, 9(4), 10-16.
- [29] Hummels, C., Redström, J., & Koskinen, I. (2007). Design research for social scientists: Reading instructions for this issue. *Knowledge, Technology & Policy*, 20(1), 11-17.
- [30] McDonagh-Philp, D., & Lebbon, C. (2000). The emotional domain in product design. *The Design Journal*, 3(1), 31-43.
- [31] Voss, A., Procter, R., Slack, R., Hartswood, M., & Rouncefield, M. (2009). Design as and for collaboration: Making sense of and supporting practical action. In A. Voss, M. Hartswood, R. Procter, M. Rouncefield, R. Slack,

& M. Büscher (Eds.), *Configuring user-designer relations: Interdisciplinary perspectives* (pp. 31-58). London: Springer.

[32] Forsythe, D. E. (1999). "It's just a matter of common sense": Ethnography as Invisible Work. *Computer Supported Cooperative Work*, 8(1/2), 127-145.

[33] Bruseberg, A., & McDonagh-Philp, D. (2001). New product development by eliciting user experience and aspirations. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 55(4), 435-452.

[34] Yin, R. K. (2008). *Case study research: Design and methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

[35] Norman, D. A. (2005). *Emotional design: Why we love (or hate) everyday things*. New York: Basic Books.

[36] Danko, S., Meneely, J., & Portillo, M. (2006). Humanizing design through narrative inquiry. *Journal of Interior Design*, 31(2), 10-28.

[37] St Pierre, L. (2002). Research and design collaboration: A case study. In J. Frascara (Ed.), *Design and the social sciences: Making connections* (pp. 135-145). London; New York: Taylor & Francis.

[38] Lawson, B. (2004). *What designers know*. Oxford [England]; Burlington, MA: Elsevier/Architectural Press.

[39] Strickler, Z., & Neafsey, P. (2002). Preventing drug interactions in older adults: A collaborative study. In J. Frascara (Ed.), *Design and the social sciences: Making connections* (pp. 102-124). London; New York: Taylor & Francis.

[40] Dishman, E. (2003). Designing for the new old: Asking, observing and performing future elders. In B. Laurel (Ed.), *Design research: Methods and perspectives* (pp. 41-48). Cambridge, Mass: The MIT Press.